

What Ukraine's 21st-Century Power System Should Really Be

(A Strategy for Transformational Transition)

"Energy cells" and "decentralized generation" — new political metaphors, or an impetus for deep reform?

"Ukraine is shaping a new architecture of energy security, built around a network of 'energy cells'." This was stated by First Deputy Prime Minister — Minister of Energy of Ukraine Denys Shmyhal in April 2026.

The more our power system degrades and is destroyed, the more effort goes not only into restoring the balance between consumption and generation, but also into attempts to model a new, modern and resilient system design. So what might a power system with an "energy cell" network architecture actually look like? It should be said that the expert community has begun actively debating the proposed novelty, which will either remain yet another beautiful metaphor or genuinely become one of the foundations of Ukraine's new energy security architecture.

Why is it so important to unpack this question? Because this is no longer simply a matter of "installing a large number of gas reciprocating cogeneration units." As L. Unihovskyi rightly noted, there does indeed exist an academic concept of cellular energy systems / energy cells, primarily in the European and German research school. But the Ukrainian public concept of "energy cells" has not yet demonstrated conformity with that model at the level of architecture, regulation, market organization, standards and operational control.

Let us first outline the overall situation in the energy sector today, to understand the boundary conditions under which the country will be implementing the new concept:

The destruction of energy facilities and critical infrastructure as a result of war crimes committed by the Russian Federation in 2022–26 not only deprived the country of an adequate balance of generating capacity, but also exposed all the accumulated problems and mistakes made in previous periods.

In 2019, Ukraine changed its wholesale electricity market model and implemented the so-called EU Third Energy Package — European Union legislation on the liberalization of the gas and electricity markets. Beyond ensuring reliable and secure electricity supply to consumers, the new model was meant to foster market relations; minimize the cost of electricity supply and the negative impact on the environment; maintain the balance between electricity supply and demand; ensure fair competition; promote electricity generation from alternative energy sources and the development of distributed generation and energy storage equipment; create conditions for attracting investment into the power sector — and many other progressive objectives essential for the sector's development.

But a negative trend that had begun long before Russia's invasion almost completely nullified the advantages of the new model: flawed state regulation, interference in tariff policy, the absence of any incentives for modernization and development, market manipulation and abuse, growing imbalances and, as a result, an accumulation of debt. For a long time this sad and depressing picture was masked by a double surplus of capacity — above all cheap nuclear and hydro power plants, which unfortunately became a source of government social populism and corruption rather than the foundation for a modern rebuild of the energy sector. Restoring the physical balance of generating capacity without resolving the accumulated systemic problems cannot be a realistic objective.

I will not dwell separately on the fact that the centralized Soviet model has finally exhausted itself, but let me list the principal differences between the old and the new models:

The existing one: large generation nodes, unidirectional flows, a passive consumer, a "blind" distribution grid, vulnerability to attack.

It is quite obvious that the core of this transformation is the development of smart, active distribution systems (smart grid), microgrids, distributed energy resources (DER), active consumers (prosumers), battery energy storage systems (BESS), electric vehicle integration (V2G), balancing capability at all levels (distributed balancing), virtual power plants (VPP), software platforms for intelligent grid management (ADMS/DERMS), and an integrated control chain from the TSO level (SCADA) down to end consumers (grid edge) — enabling the transition from the traditional one-way system to a decentralized one.

It should be noted that all of the above elements of the future architecture of the Integrated Power System (IPS) of Ukraine are, to some degree, being actively discussed in each area; international standards are being adapted; and there are already many examples of successfully implemented DER, BESS and microgrid projects. But this process is slow, unsystematic and uncoordinated, with the result that the development of some technologies is held back by the absence of others.

Let me give an example. In 2022–23, after the first waves of destruction, measures for the simultaneous deployment of distributed generation (DER) and smart grids were drawn up and approved by the National Security and Defense Council of Ukraine (NSDC). When the efficiency of the commissioned distributed generation was analyzed for a single cold day in February of this year — with an average air temperature of $-15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ across the country and consumers being disconnected for 12–16 hours — it turned out that the average capacity utilization factor of DER on that day was only 28%!!! One of the main reasons: the absence of smart grids and telemetry at the substations to which the DER are connected. And it is obvious that as DER volumes grow, this problem will only worsen. An even bigger problem arises with the utilization efficiency of solar and wind plants, whose stochastic output is causing ever greater economic losses.

The conclusion is that for Ukraine, the challenge of rebuilding the power sector lies not only in a generation deficit, but also in a grid controllability deficit. Every hryvnia invested in the digitalization and automation of the grids can deliver a greater effect from the existing distributed

generation than a hryvnia invested in building additional generation. A simple example: if the capacity utilization factor of distributed generation stood at 60%, that would effectively equal €250–300 million in avoided construction costs for every gigawatt of capacity. If we add the other components of the cumulative effect of grid modernization — those cited, for example, by CIGRE in its studies — modernization becomes unavoidable not only technically but economically. A few figures: grid losses reduced by up to 20%, with a simultaneous 25–40% increase in network hosting capacity without massive construction; outage duration cut by up to 40%; and the headline effect — 100% integration of DER!

At the beginning of the year, the head of NPC “Ukrenergo” announced the need to build 9.5 GW of new generation in Ukraine's power system in the near future. This concerns highly flexible gas-fired generation, biofuel-fired thermal power plants, energy storage facilities and “green” generation. The required investment for this program may exceed €8 billion. It is easy enough to calculate the losses if grid modernization continues to lag behind the development of distributed — and therefore resilient to today's threats — sources of heat and electricity.

Ukraine is already investing billions in distributed energy resources. The key question of the next stage is whether the power system will be able to use them effectively.

Why does terminology matter?

Against this backdrop, a debate is spreading in the opposite direction. As the Energy Club website reports, during the energy forum “Energy Decentralization 2026: Generation, Storage, Financing,” the president of the NGO “CIGRE-Ukraine” Oleksandr Svetelik stressed: “We need to define what decentralized generation actually is. In the sense we currently attach to this notion, it is above all backup generation for individual enterprises. We need new projects, new economic relationships, new innovative proposals. We have created an aggregator which, in our view, should unite everything and provide an interface to our central dispatcher. We need a unified, single, integrated power system. If the system is not like that, only backup generation will operate. No islands, no clusters. We use many terms, but so far there are no projects — at least, I have not seen them.”

Before moving further into the transformation of the Integrated Power System (IPS) of Ukraine toward a new architecture, I would like to examine the statement of a colleague I hold in high regard — all the more so because such statements are not uncommon among politicians and certain sector experts whose opinions are quoted and influence the outcome of strategic decisions.

So, taking Oleksandr Dmytrovych's statement point by point:

"Decentralized generation" vs. "distributed generation"

In Ukraine's professional and regulatory domain, the term actually used is distributed generation. This is not merely a linguistic difference. “Decentralized generation” is often used in Ukraine as a political-economic term, whereas “distributed generation” describes a specific technical model of siting generating capacity within the grid. So when distributed generation is reduced to the role of

"backup generation for enterprises," the question arises: are we talking about the regulatory concept, or about some particular management doctrine?

"We have created an aggregator"

The very word "aggregator" looks ambiguous here. In the modern power industry, an aggregator is not a dispatch superstructure sitting above the entire system. Typically, an aggregator:

- pools a group of producers, consumers or storage assets;
- acts as a market participant;
- provides balancing services;
- interacts with the transmission or distribution system operator through standardized interfaces.

That is why the phrase "an aggregator ... should unite everything and provide an interface to our central dispatcher" sounds rather odd to a professional. It evokes a "single control center" architecture, whereas modern power systems are built as multi-level control systems.

"Our central dispatcher"

This wording, too, raises questions. In a modern power system there is no need for every element to interface directly with the central dispatcher. There is a hierarchy: the local controller of an installation; the microgrid controller; the grid operator's SCADA; EMS/DMS systems; control centers at various levels. The philosophy of modern grid control consists not in concentrating all commands in one center, but in distributing functions and automating decision-making.

The conflict with the Smart Grid and Microgrid concepts

The most contentious thesis is: "No islands, no clusters."

Because:

- Smart Grid presupposes substantial autonomy of nodes;
- a microgrid is, by definition, characterized by the ability to operate both grid-connected and in island mode;
- modern power system resilience standards in fact call for segmentation and the localization of disturbances.

After the large-scale blackouts in the USA, Japan and Europe, one of the development directions adopted was precisely the creation of controllable microgrids — not the reinforcement of absolute centralization.

For me, the most debatable point is not the idea of a unified power system itself, but the implicit equation of two notions: unified power system = single control center. In modern architecture these are not the same thing.

One can have:

- a single synchronous power system;
- single market rules;

- single dispatch procedures;

and at the same time:

- thousands of distributed generation facilities;
- local energy clusters;
- microgrids;
- energy storage;
- automated control at the grid edge.

This is exactly how the concepts of Smart Grid, Microgrid, Virtual Power Plant (VPP) and aggregated distributed energy resources (DER) are evolving.

Hence the statement about "an aggregator that will unite everything and provide an interface to the central dispatcher" is more reminiscent of the logic of the traditional vertically integrated power system of the 20th century than of the architecture of modern digital energy, where control is hierarchical, distributed and largely automated.

It seems to me that the quotations above reveal not only a terminology problem, but a collision of two different paradigms of power system development.

In the language of standards and current practice, the objects of control today increasingly are: distributed energy resources (DER), microgrids, virtual power plants (VPP), battery energy storage systems (BESS), and active consumers (prosumers). The dispatch center does not directly control every inverter or gas reciprocating unit. It sets constraints, operating regimes, market signals and system service requirements. A substantial share of decisions is taken automatically at lower levels.

That is why the phrase "the aggregator should unite everything and provide an interface to our central dispatcher" is ambiguous — also because it is unclear what exactly the author calls an aggregator. In world practice, an aggregator is, as a rule, a market or technological intermediary between many small resources and the system operator. It does not substitute for the Smart Grid architecture or for SCADA.

Even more interesting is the assertion: "No islands, no clusters." Here I see a potential contradiction with Ukraine's experience of recent years. During the massive attacks on energy infrastructure, many experts began to speak precisely about increasing the survivability of the system through: distributed generation, local energy centers, cogeneration units for communities, and the capability of critical infrastructure to operate autonomously.

In other words, the question is no longer only about efficiency, but about resilience.

And here a fundamental question for debate arises:

Should distributed generation be regarded merely as an auxiliary element of the Ukrainian IPS, or should it become a separate, equal layer of the power system with the capability of local autonomy in emergency conditions?

In my view, it is precisely around this question that the real dividing line runs between adherents of the classical centralized model and proponents of the Smart Grid / Microgrid concepts.

Ukraine genuinely needs a transition to a new power system architecture: Smart Grids, active distribution systems, microgrids, DER, prosumers, storage, V2G, distributed intelligence and cyber-secure digital coordination from the TSO down to the grid edge. But this transformation must rest on professional international and regulatory terminology — not on media metaphors that have no clearly defined technical, regulatory or investment content.

Minister of Energy Denys Shmyhal has stated that the full recovery and modernization of the country's energy sector will require attracting more than 90 billion dollars over the next ten years. This means that the Ukrainian side's understanding of terms such as bankability, regulatory clarity, operator responsibility, investment structure, interoperability, due diligence, standards and many others must coincide with those commonly established among foreign investors and lenders.

This is not my first discussion of this kind, but let me repeat: if the purpose is merely to explain an idea, then one may indeed say "decentralized generation" or a network of "energy cells." But if we are talking about a state concept, a development program, an investment package, international financing or regulatory change, the term must meet entirely different criteria.

It must be:

- legally defined;
- technically specified;
- embedded in the regulatory framework;
- intelligible to DSOs/the TSO/NEURC;
- usable in a tariff or contractual model;
- intelligible to IFIs, DFIs, banks, donors, insurance agencies and EPC contractors;
- suitable for due diligence.

Otherwise it will not be accepted by banks as a bankable concept — it will remain a communication concept.

If these questions are answered with the words "energy cell," the investor will understand nothing. If they are answered in terms of distributed generation, a microgrid, a local energy hub, energy storage, controllable load, the DSO, an aggregator, a PPA, a tariff model and operational responsibility — then a substantive conversation begins.

The moment we move to financing, terminology becomes part of risk allocation. An imprecise term means:

- regulatory risk;
- risk of undefined ownership;
- risk of tariff ineligibility;
- risk of an absent repayment source;

- risk of non-alignment with the DSO/TSO;
- risk of costs not being recognized in the tariff;
- risk of being unable to conclude a bankable PPA;
- risk of uninsurability;
- risk of being impossible to scale.

The greatest challenge for the Ukrainian IPS in the coming decade may prove to be not a deficit of generation, but a lack of system controllability amid the rapid growth of DER.

A strategic crossroads

Ukraine stands at a strategic fork in the road. The rebuilding and reconstruction of the power system must not be a return to 2021 — it must be a leap to 2031.

I am convinced that we have the chance to use post-war reconstruction not to restore the old energy sector, but to create one of Europe's most resilient and adaptive large-scale power systems — a powerful infrastructure capable of carrying the new economy of the state.

Let us briefly summarize what the USSR left us as a legacy.

The Soviet architecture:

- Large central generation, with a capacity surplus of 20 GW;
- Top-down dispatch;
- Transmission-centric energy delivery — traditional: NPP/TPP/HPP → high-voltage lines → consumer;
- Passive load;
- Deterministic flows — pre-defined, fixed volumes of electricity scheduled for transfer between system nodes;
- "Blind" distribution networks (minimum observability at distribution level);
- Dependence on baseload generation / almost no flexibility mechanisms.

The changes of recent years (2015–2026):

- 70% of thermal power plants destroyed, 6 GW of nuclear capacity lost, a 10 GW capacity deficit;
- Renewables (solar PV, wind), distributed generation, energy storage;
- Balancing problems: stochastic generation creates sharp swings (variance) in power output, complicating the maintenance of supply-demand balance in the system.

Now let us think through, step by step and logically, what architecture we can arrive at.

In the 2021 model, the dispatcher saw a relatively small number of large facilities: nuclear plants; thermal plants; hydro plants; a few large wind farms; a few large solar plants.

The system was complex, but controllable through a limited number of nodes. In effect, the architecture was: few producers → millions of consumers. It was for this model that the forecast energy balances, the transmission system code, operating regimes and dispatch procedures were created.

Now imagine Ukraine in 2031. Roughly:

- hundreds of thousands of rooftop solar installations;
- tens of thousands of commercial storage units;
- thousands of industrial microgrids;
- hundreds of thousands of electric vehicles with V2G;
- thousands of cogeneration units;
- flexibility aggregators;
- energy communities;
- local energy hubs.

In such a system, the dispatcher physically cannot control each resource individually, because this is a different class of system altogether. **And the problem is not that centralized control is no longer needed. The problem is that centralized control is no longer sufficient.** These are fundamentally different statements.

The Ukrainian IPS in 2031 will still require:

- a system operator;
- system-wide balancing;
- management of power flows;
- frequency reserves;
- coordination with ENTSO-E;
- system-wide cybersecurity;
- centralized emergency control.

In other words, the TSO does not disappear. What changes is what exactly it controls.

An analogy can be drawn with the Internet. The telephone network of the 20th century resembled classical power engineering: centralized nodes; a rigid hierarchy; deterministic routes. Today the Internet works differently: distributed routing; local decision-making; global coordination through protocols. Nobody controls every packet from a single center. Yet the network remains unified. It is precisely toward this type of architecture that the power industry is gradually moving.

That is why, in O. Svetelik's quote — "We have created an aggregator which should unite everything and provide an interface to our central dispatcher" — what troubles me most is not even the word "aggregator," but the phrase "unite everything." Because modern architecture does not envisage uniting everything into a single point of control. It envisages multi-level coordination.

Simplified, the 2031 model looks more like this:

TSO

↓ *coordination of system-level parameters*

DSO + ADMS

↓ *local grid control*

DERMS / Aggregators

↓ *coordination of distributed resources*

Microgrids / Energy Hubs

↓ *local optimization*

Prosumers / EV / Storage / DER

After 2022, one more criterion emerged for Ukraine that was virtually absent from pre-war energy planning: system resilience. In Soviet and post-Soviet logic, the key indicator was reliability. In the new reality an additional question arises: what happens after part of the system is lost? This is exactly where:

- microgrids;
- distributed intelligence;
- local balancing;
- islanding capability;
- DER orchestration;

cease to be buzzwords and become elements of the defense capability of critical infrastructure.

Therefore, the architecture of Ukrainian future IPS must remain a single synchronous system under TSO coordination, but control within it must become multi-level, distributed and digital. Decisions must be taken as close as possible to the point where an event occurs, while the central level coordinates the system rather than attempting to directly control every resource.

In my view, this is precisely the key difference between "rebuilding what was" and "building the next-generation power system."

Returning to the start of our discussion, we can finally draw the conclusion that was worth this long debate — one that allows us to avoid a common error, whereby the discussion is artificially reduced to a choice between two extremes:

- a rigidly centralized Soviet-type system;
- a set of autonomous islands with no unified control.

In reality, modern architecture lies between these extremes.

What actually changes? In the classical model, the TSO performed almost all balancing through a relatively small number of large power plants. Schematically: TSO → NPP/TPP/HPP → DSO → Consumer. In the new architecture, several new layers of control emerge: TSO + SCADA → DSO + ADMS → DERMS / Aggregator → Microgrid EMS → DER / Storage / EV / Prosumer. And each layer acquires its own zone of responsibility.

The new role of the Distribution System Operator

In my opinion, this is where the deepest transformation lies. Historically, Ukrainian DSOs were primarily owners and operators of network assets: lines, transformers, substations. In effect, they managed infrastructure. But with a large volume of distributed energy resources (DER), this is no longer enough. The DSO is gradually becoming:

- an active network operator;
- a coordinator of local flexibility;
- a DER integrator;
- a source of grid data;
- a local balancing operator.

What is taking place is an evolution from a traditional asset-based distribution utility to an "Active Distribution System Operator."

What is delegated to the microgrid level. A microgrid should not have to clear every second of its battery's or inverter's operation with the TSO's or DSO's dispatcher. It decides for itself: how to use its storage; when to start cogeneration; how to balance local loads; how to optimize its own consumption. What matters to the external system is the outcome. For example: at the point of common coupling, I guarantee not to exceed a defined import or export of power. The internal logic remains local. This is what distributed intelligence is.

Why did my colleague's phrase "no clusters" strike a nerve? Because technically the modern system already consists of clusters. Not necessarily in the geographic sense, but functionally — yes:

- an industrial park with its own generation;
- a hospital complex with BESS;
- a port energy hub;
- a municipal microgrid;
- an energy community.

All of these are, in effect, local controllable subsystems. And this does not contradict the existence of a unified IPS.

At this stage of the discussion we can draw another intermediate conclusion:

The future Ukrainian IPS must not turn into a set of isolated microgrids, but neither can it remain a system in which all decisions are taken exclusively by the central dispatcher. It must evolve into a multi-level architecture in which the TSO provides system-level coordination, DSOs operate active distribution networks, and microgrids and DER platforms perform local balancing and resource control in real time.

The logic of a power system architecture that does not centralize all decisions, but distributes them across levels

Now, setting secondary matters aside, let us formulate the basic principle:

The Ukrainian IPS in 2031 is a single integrated cyber-physical energy system built on Smart Grid principles, in which centralized system coordination by the TSO is combined with distributed control at the level of DSOs, microgrids, aggregators and active consumers.

This allows us to define the correct architecture.

Level 1. The Transmission System Operator remains the system integrator. In the new architecture the TSO's role does not diminish — on the contrary, it becomes more complex. The TSO is responsible for: system stability; the capacity balance; frequency; cross-border flows; integration with ENTSO-E; emergency control; system reserves; cybersecurity at the critical level. There is no dismantling of dispatch control — rather, its functions change and deepen.

Level 2. Distribution System Operators become active network operators (Smart Grid). This is where the greatest transformation will take place. The functions of the DSO in 2031: active distribution system operator; local balancing; DER integration; flexibility management; congestion management; forecasting of local operating conditions; coordination of microgrids; interaction with aggregators.

This requires: an Advanced Distribution Management System (ADMS); a Distributed Energy Resource Management System (DERMS); monitoring and state estimation of the network's current operating state; the operator's ability to see, control and analyze the state of the electricity network at distribution level (10/0.4 kV) — observability at distribution level; digital substations; Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI).

Level 3. Microgrids as a new functional element. A microgrid is not an alternative to the IPS, but a structural element of it. A microgrid can: operate synchronously with the grid; balance resources locally; optimize its own consumption; transition to island mode and ensure automatic reconnection to the IPS; sustain critical load. In normal operation, the microgrid remains part of the IPS. No fragmentation — on the contrary, coordinated integration.

Level 4. Aggregators as a new market institution. Recall one of the principal errors in the quotation above. The aggregator must not be "a single gateway to the central dispatcher." Its role is different. An aggregator: pools thousands of small resources; assembles a controllable capacity portfolio; participates in the ancillary services market; provides flexibility services; interacts with the TSO and DSOs through standardized interfaces. The aggregator is thus a market intermediary and resource coordinator — not a new dispatch vertical.

Level 5. The prosumer becomes a full participant in the system. A prosumer can simultaneously: consume; generate; store; sell flexibility services; participate in a VPP; contribute to balancing. This is the transition from passive load to active grid participant.

Level 6. A new telecommunications foundation. IPS-2031 is no longer merely an energy system. It is an energy-and-information system. Its foundations are: SCADA convergence; utility-grade

IP/MPLS; IEC 61850; IEC 61970/61968 (CIM); PMU/WAMS; edge computing; distributed telemetry; OT cybersecurity. The information infrastructure effectively becomes as important as the power lines and substations.

Level 7. A new control logic. Here, in my view, lies the principal difference from the 2021 architecture. It was: centralized adoption of most decisions. It becomes: hierarchical, distributed decision-making. For example: an inverter regulates reactive power locally; a BESS stabilizes a local node; a microgrid performs its own balancing; the DSO relieves local congestion; the TSO maintains system frequency. Each level solves its own task.

The future system does not centralize all decisions — it distributes them across levels.

To describe the concept concisely:

The Ukrainian IPS in 2031 is a single integrated Smart Grid platform in which the TSO ensures system coordination and reliability, DSOs operate active distribution networks, microgrids perform local balancing, aggregators integrate distributed resources, and prosumers become full participants in the electricity market.

The technical (physical) model of the future power system

If we accept the proposed concept, we can move on to the technical, or physical, model of the future power system — which, in countries that began this work long ago, is usually decomposed into four layers:

Layer 1. The Physical Grid Layer

This is the physical infrastructure for the transmission and distribution of electricity.

The Transmission System Operator level. Functions: synchronous operation of the IPS; bulk transmission; cross-border flows; system-wide balancing; emergency control; integration with ENTSO-E. Assets: 220–750 kV overhead lines; bulk transmission substations; relay protection and automation systems; WAMS/PMU.

The Distribution System Operator level. Functions: active management of the distribution network; local balancing; DER integration; congestion management; power quality support. Assets: 0.4–150 kV networks; digital substations; Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI); an Advanced Distribution Management System (ADMS).

The Microgrid level. Functions: local optimization; local generation; local balancing; island mode; black start for critical loads. Typical facilities: industrial parks; hospitals; water utilities; military installations; municipal energy hubs.

The Prosumer level. Functions: consumption; generation; storage; controllable load; participation in flexibility markets. Typical assets: rooftop solar PV; home BESS; heat pumps; EV/V2G.

Layer 2. The Energy Resources Layer (Generation and DER)

In the 2031 system, production is no longer concentrated solely in large power plants.

Central generation. It remains the backbone: nuclear plants; hydro plants; pumped-storage plants; large CHP plants; large wind and solar farms. Their role: system capacity; reserves; frequency regulation; baseload coverage of demand.

DER (Distributed Energy Resources). They become the system's second great circuit. Composition: cogeneration; biogas; rooftop solar; local wind; battery energy storage systems (BESS); electric vehicles (EV); demand response. Functions: local balancing; flexibility; backup; grid support.

VPP (Virtual Power Plant). A new aggregated layer. It pools: thousands of DER; behind-the-meter storage; electric vehicles; active consumers. To the TSO or DSO, a VPP looks like a single dispatchable resource.

Layer 3. The Digital Grid Layer (information topology)

This is where the main difference between the 2021 and 2031 models lies. The power system becomes data-driven.

The Field Layer. Devices: remote terminal units (RTU); intelligent electronic devices (IED); smart meters; phasor measurement units (PMU); inverters; BESS controllers. Purpose: telemetry; local automation; measurement.

The Communications Layer. Foundation: a fiber-optic network; a reliable IP/MPLS backbone; utility-grade Ethernet; backup LTE/5G channels. Principle: every node becomes observable.

The Control Layer. Systems: SCADA; EMS; ADMS; DERMS; OMS; GIS. This is where the digital twin of the grid is formed.

The Aggregation Layer. Platforms: VPP; flexibility platforms; market platforms; balancing interfaces.

The control principle. Not: the center controls everything. But: local decision + global coordination.

Layer 4. The Cyber Layer (cybersecurity)

By 2031 this is no longer a separate module. It is a cross-cutting layer of the entire architecture.

TSO level. Protection of: control centers; EMS; cross-border interfaces; critical substations.

DSO level. Protection of: ADMS; digital substations; AMI; field devices.

DER level. Protection of: inverters; BESS; EV chargers; DERMS. This is where the greatest number of new attack surfaces emerges.

Core principles: Zero Trust Architecture (ZTA); IT/OT segmentation; PKI and digital certificates; a dedicated energy-sector SOC; OT traffic monitoring; secure remote access; cyber resilience of critical infrastructure.

Beneath all these layers operate, simultaneously: the physical electricity grid; the digital data network; and the cybersecurity systems. IPS-2031 can thus be defined as a single integrated cyber-physical power system in which flows of energy, information and control commands circulate simultaneously from the TSO level down to the prosumer and back. It is precisely the bidirectionality of energy and information flows that constitutes the main difference from the 2021 architecture.

System transformation: from the architecture model to the new state (Roadmap)

For Ukraine it is especially critical to transform the system correctly and without mistakes. We are not building the system "from scratch." We must modernize a system that:

- operates 24/7;
- is under constant threat of physical attack;
- is already synchronized with ENTSO-E;
- has a mixed equipment fleet ranging from Soviet-era to state-of-the-art;
- cannot be shut down for modernization.

Hence the key principle of the roadmap: **evolution without loss of controllability and resilience.**

I. Grid digitalization (2026–2031)

Goal: transition from partial to full observability of the grid.

Current state. Many DSO networks remain effectively "blind": no grid telemetry on feeders; limited load control; no information on DER; insufficient granularity of 0.4–35 kV operating data.

First-priority steps: digital substations; AMI/smart metering; DER telemetry; distribution grid state estimation; GIS + asset management.

Result: the DSO begins to see its network in near real time.

II. Convergence: SCADA → Smart Grid Platform

This stage is among the riskiest.

What we have now: SCADA + RTU; serial protocols; DNP3; IEC 60870-5-101; IEC 60870-5-104; Modbus; TDM architectures. The logic: RTU → SCADA → dispatcher.

What we want to achieve: IEC 61850 Digital Substation Architecture — IED ↔ Process Bus ↔ Station Bus ↔ SCADA/EMS.

The main risk is attempting a revolutionary cutover — switch off the old, switch on the new. For a power system this is unacceptable. The correct strategy is therefore:

Stage 1 — a hybrid environment. Operating in parallel: IEC 101; IEC 104; DNP3; Modbus; IEC 61850 via gateway solutions.

Stage 2 — IEC 61850 at new substations. All new construction: digital-by-default; process bus; GOOSE; MMS; sampled values.

Stage 3 — gradual migration of legacy facilities. Without loss of dispatch controllability.

III. Synchronization of energy and information systems

The importance of time is often underestimated here. In the old system, seconds were acceptable. In the new one, PMU, DERMS, VPP and flexibility markets demand microsecond precision. Required: GPS timing; PTP IEEE 1588; synchronized measurements; wide-area monitoring. In effect, a new resource emerges: unified system time.

IV. Virtualization of control

In my view, this is one of the least discussed topics. The future power system will be controlled not through individual physical devices, but through logical resources. For example: 1,000 home batteries — one VPP resource. 100 industrial loads — one flexibility portfolio. 500 EV charging points — one controllable resource. This is the true virtualization of energy.

V. Distributed intelligence

The most important transition.

It was: event → center → decision → command.

It becomes: event → local decision ↓ coordination with the higher level.

For example: an inverter regulates voltage; a BESS smooths a local peak; a microgrid performs local balancing; the DSO merely coordinates.

VI. Cybersecurity

Here, in my opinion, Ukraine is obliged to outpace many countries — because we already have unique experience of attacks on the energy sector. But it is also here that the greatest danger of convergence is hidden. In the old system: SCADA was a closed network. In the new one: SCADA – ADMS – DERMS – AMI – EV – VPP – Cloud. Cybersecurity must therefore be not a separate project, but a requirement at every stage. Principles: Zero Trust; OT SOC; PKI; IEC 62351; network segmentation; secure remote access; security by design.

VII. Stages of Roadmap-2031

Stage 1 (2026–2027) — Visibility: telemetry; digital substations; AMI; DER inventory.

Stage 2 (2027–2028) — Integration: ADMS; DERMS; IEC 61850; CIM; utility IP/MPLS.

Stage 3 (2028–2029) — Flexibility: aggregators; VPP; flexibility markets; active DSO.

Stage 4 (2029–2031) — Autonomous Smart Grid: distributed intelligence; automated balancing; microgrid orchestration; large-scale DER participation.

SCADA convergence must be one of the central principles of the entire program:

Modernization must not destroy the existing operational controllability of the power system. The transition from classical SCADA/RTU architectures to IEC 61850 digital substations and IP/MPLS communications must proceed in stages, through hybrid environments, with guaranteed preservation of dispatch control, relay protection, emergency control automation and cyber resilience at every stage of the transformation.

VIII. The cybersecurity of the near future

In my view, this issue is already rising to the level of a strategic question for the entire future of the Ukrainian IPS.

An important particularity: while we are partially restoring the physical grid, the information architecture we must in effect build anew — drawing not on the legacy of the 1980s–2000s, but on the requirements of the 2030s.

A clear understanding is needed here: **you cannot simply "add cybersecurity."** Many utilities historically built it this way: SCADA → network → then add a firewall → call it cybersecurity. By 2031 this no longer works. The future architecture must be built on the principle of **Security by Architecture** — cybersecurity as a property of the system, not a separate subsystem.

What should the information topology of IPS-2031 be? The answer: not a single network, but a multi-layer system.

Layer 1. The critical transport level (Utility Backbone). Foundation: fiber-optic lines; IP/MPLS; a segmented architecture; redundant routes. In effect this is the data-transport analogue of the bulk power grid, carrying: EMS; SCADA; PMU; WAMS; inter-control-center communication.

Layer 2. The operational network (OT Network). A separate operational network. Not the corporate IT network. Not the Internet. The OT domain proper, where the following operate: digital substations; IEDs; RTUs; protection and automation; GOOSE; Sampled Values.

Layer 3. The distributed energy resources domain (DER Domain). The greatest complexity — millions of devices: inverters; BESS; EVs; charging stations; smart meters; heat pumps; home EMS. They cannot be connected directly into the TSO's critical perimeter. Many vendors from many countries with differing risk profiles — hence the need for multi-level isolation.

Layer 4. The Market & Flexibility Layer. A separate domain that allows market participants — network operators and aggregators — to trade flexibility in consumption or generation. It pools home batteries, electric vehicles and heat pumps to balance the grid and prevent congestion. Here operate: aggregators; VPPs; flexibility markets; energy communities. This level must be separated from operational control systems.

Not: everyone connected to everyone. But: **Zero Trust Domains**, where each level has its own trust perimeter, its own authorization, its own access control.

In all likelihood, Ukraine will face the problem of AI-enabled cyber attacks at scale. An adversary that already exists will gain a new capability — at a scale hard to imagine today — to automatically: analyze the network; map assets; hunt for vulnerabilities; generate exploits; conduct coordinated attacks.

IPS-2031 therefore needs not only the communication protocol standard (IEC 61850), the Common Information Model (CIM), DERMS and ADMS — but also the integration of AI into response and monitoring centers (AI-assisted SOC); behavioral analytics; anomaly detection; autonomous incident response; and digital twins for cyber ranges.

The information architecture of the Ukrainian IPS in 2031 must be built as a multi-domain cyber-physical platform with full observability, segmented trust levels, a Zero Trust Architecture (ZTA), cryptographic agility for the transition to post-quantum standards, and a built-in capability to counter automated AI-driven cyberattacks.

It is precisely information architecture and cybersecurity that should become the field in which Ukraine is capable not of catching up, but of setting standards. The experience of attacks on its energy sector, integration with the European system, and the need to build a substantial part of the infrastructure practically from scratch create a unique — albeit very costly — window of opportunity for this.

EPILOGUE. On the main problem of transforming and rebuilding the new power system

One can draw an ideal architecture with IEC 61850, CIM, ADMS, DERMS, VPP, Zero Trust and post-quantum cryptography, but a simple question remains:

Who will design, deploy, operate and maintain all of this? How do we assemble the "dream team" capable of delivering it?

Once basic financing is secured, it is workforce capability that may become the main constraint on the pace of the IPS-2031 transformation.

In effect, Ukraine needs a new engineering industry. Not just power engineers — a new professional ecosystem at the intersection of: power engineering; telecommunications; automation; software engineering; cybersecurity; systems integration. That is, people who simultaneously

understand: relay protection; IEC 61850; MPLS; Linux; OT cybersecurity; DERMS; SCADA; power system operation.

Let me name the key professions and competencies that must be addressed as a first priority:

Systems architects. This is the brain center. Roughly 80–100 people of the highest caliber are needed. Competencies: power systems; grid modernization; utility architecture; CIM; IEC 61850; ENTSO-E; utility telecom. Their task: not to build, but to design the system as a whole.

Power engineers. The largest group. Areas: substations; transmission lines; relay protection and automation; operational dispatch control; DER integration; power quality.

Utility telecom engineers. Without them, Smart Grid does not exist. Needed: IP/MPLS; DWDM; packet transport; synchronization; utility communications. This is effectively a separate discipline.

SCADA / ADMS / DERMS engineers. The greatest shortage. Specialists who understand power engineering, automation and programming. It is they who create the system's digital layer.

A dedicated energy OT cyber defense center. Not just IT security — OT security specifically. Needed: specialists in IEC 62351; industrial cybersecurity; incident response; threat intelligence; SOC; digital substations.

Software & data engineers. A separate category. The energy sector of the future will be software-defined. Needed: backend developers; distributed systems engineers; AI engineers; GIS engineers; data architects.

Integrators. The most valuable people — those who can put it all together. Who know: the electricity grid; automation; telecom; cybersecurity; business processes.

Educational mobilization. In effect, a training program: universities; DSO training centers; digital substation laboratories; cyber ranges; dispatcher simulators; Smart Grid centers.

Who could form the core. The core of the future team should be drawn from: NPC Ukrenergo; the largest DSOs; specialized universities; Ukrainian systems integrators; telecom companies; critical infrastructure cyber defense centers; the Ministry of Digital Transformation and the Ukrainian IT sector.

Conclusions

Frankly speaking, the question of rebuilding and transforming the Ukrainian IPS, as presented here, goes far beyond technology and resources. It is now a question of the institutional capability of the state. At the state level — the top leadership: the President, the Verkhovna Rada, the Government — there is no longer either time or choice about whether or not to pursue this program.

I have deliberately not raised here the questions discussed most at government meetings and in the public space:

- how many GW to build;
- how much BESS to install;
- how much funding to raise;
- how many gas reciprocating stations to procure.

That will be the easiest task compared with the stated challenge of creating one of one of Europe's most resilient and adaptive large-scale power systems — a powerful infrastructure capable of carrying the new economy of the state. And this is not only about energy. The infrastructure to be created on the basis of the power grids must also become the backbone of a future AI-enabled economy — an economy in which millions of AI agents manage transport, healthcare, industry and the public sector.

I have also deliberately refrained from setting out CAPEX/OPEX figures or revenue and payback models. First, this question depends directly on the implementation timeline, which the state must define for itself. If the state considers this a strategic, first-order priority, then the sources of financing must not be market-based alone. Second, the volume of investment will depend on the chosen depth and pace of the transformation. If, for example, DSOs move at their own discretion, according to the resources available to them — that is, RAB tariffs — then deploying Smart Grid by 2032 is improbable, since experts estimate the full digitalization of a single DSO at €1 billion and more. This is why state decisions are needed: any timeline holds only if a state financing program is adopted and subsequently honored.

The problem is that the question "Who will design, build and operate IPS-2031?" does not fall within the competence of any single person. It lies at the intersection of energy, education, digitalization, security, defense and industrial policy.

To whom should this question be addressed, by virtue of office?

The Minister of Energy, the Minister of Digital Transformation and the Minister of Economy. The ministries must initiate the reform and make the case for it at the highest level. It must be a comprehensive state program with the corresponding legislative and regulatory support and financing — and, above all, the political will to deliver it. The Ministry of Energy must also provide the answers on: generation; the capacity balance; grid restoration; financing volumes. The Ministry of Energy must bring together the people who are responsible for the system's operation every day: the heads of companies of all forms of ownership; scientific and engineering centers; chief dispatchers; technical directors; chief digital transformation officers; heads of Smart Grid programs; heads of critical infrastructure cyber defense centers.

The leadership of NPC Ukrenergo. It is the TSO that will have to live inside this new architecture. The leadership of Ukrenergo should play a central role in shaping IPS-2031.

The Chair of the National Energy and Utilities Regulatory Commission (NEURC). Without the regulator there will be: no aggregator role; no flexibility markets; no tariffs for the new type of DSO; no incentives for digitalization. It is NEURC that effectively determines whether the

DSO remains “a traditional asset-based distribution utility” or becomes an “active distribution system operator.”

In closing, let me state the central thesis of this entire analysis:

Ukraine's reconstruction challenge is no longer limited to replacing lost generation capacity. It increasingly involves building the operational, digital and institutional capabilities required to manage millions of distributed energy resources.

Sergiy Yermilov,

Former Minister of Energy of Ukraine (2000-2001, 2002-2004)